

ALL-Ready Project Deliverable 5.3

ALL-Ready – The European Agroecology Living Lab and Research Infrastructure Network: Preparation phase

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Report on the capacity building validation activity and workshops

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List of abbreviations

Agroecology	AE
Agroecology Living Labs	AELLS
Capacity Building	CB
Capacity Building Programme	CBP
Computer Vision Centre	CVC
Coordination and Support Action	CSA
European Commission	EC
European Network of Living Labs	ENoLL
European Union	EU
Horizon Europe	HE
Integrated Pest Management	IPM
Key Performance Indicators	KPIs
Lighthouse	LH
Living Labs	LLs
Pilot Network	PN
Pilot Network Members	PNMs
Performance Enhancement Platform	PEP
Research Infrastructures	RIs
Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona	UAB
Work package	WP

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Executive summary

Currently, agricultural systems confront multiple environmental and socio-economic challenges, encompassing climate change, biodiversity decline, lack of resources, deterioration of soil and water quality, fluctuating prices, low incomes, and generation renewal. Agroecology (AE) has the potential to enhance the sustainability and resilience of farming systems, thereby playing a vital role in tackling these issues.

Living Labs (LLs) and Research Infrastructures (RIs) represent powerful tools with significant potential for advancing AE in Europe. For this reason, the ALL-Ready project has aimed to establish a foundation for a forthcoming European network of LLs and RIs aimed at facilitating the widespread adoption of AE across the European continent.

ALL-Ready is a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) funded by the European Commission (EC) with the aim of preparing a framework for a future network of living labs and research infrastructures that will enable the transition towards AE throughout Europe. Based on the premise that AE can strengthen the sustainability and resilience of farming systems, the project contributes to addressing the multiple challenges that they are facing today including climate change, loss of biodiversity, dwindling resources, and degradation of soil and water quality.

The project established the foundational elements and provided the essential requirements and actions to launch the mentioned partnership. The project is based on a deeply participatory and all-encompassing approach, including real-life experimentation, effectively employing a living lab methodology. A fundamental principle of this project is the active involvement of stakeholders, which has already commenced during the preparation of this proposal.

One of ALL-Ready's goals is to lay the groundwork for the capacity building programme (CBP) development in support of the AE transition within LLs and RIs. This effort, led by the European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL) and its certified living lab member EV ILVO, involves several stages, such as identifying the essential skills required for LLs and RIs, as well as piloting an ALL-Ready CBP.

To test and enhance the CBP, the pilot network members (PNMs) of ALL-Ready have actively participated. The primary goal of the ALL-Ready project is to establish a pilot network (PN) comprising Agroecology Living Labs (AELs), RIs, and other open innovation arrangements across Europe. This network serves as a testbed for experimentation, feedback collection on tools and recommendations, and building cooperation among diverse agroecology-focused LLs and RIs. The PN facilitates real-life experimentation on the structuring and functioning of the future European network, employing co-creative and participatory methods. Lessons learned directly inform the setup of the future network and EU partnerships.

This report provides an overview of the main findings resulting from all the phases of the CBP, meaning scoping, prototyping, implementation, testing and validation. It outlines the challenges encountered during the activities organised within WP5 and offers recommendations for the creation of new curricula and training programmes. The insights gained from the ALL-Ready pilot network contribute to the ongoing development of AgroEcoLLNet and other linking initiatives and projects, fostering the growth and sustainability of agroecology practices in Europe.

Linked to the activities of the WP5, four regional workshops in Europe identified gaps in skills and knowledge, conducted collaboratively by WP4 and WP5 in Seville, Budapest, Frankfurt, and Helsinki. The workshops involved diverse participants from multiple countries, fostering discussions on competencies, regional gaps, and the role of local actors in supporting development. By collecting the feedback received through the workshop and the interviews with the ALL-Ready project partners, the following recommendations for capacity building in agroecology can be summarised:

- Integrating systems thinking into policy instruments and future networks can foster an understanding of agroecological system dynamics and relationships.

- It is essential to create a universally accepted narrative for a broader understanding of agroecology as a concept and to embed it across education and advisory services. It is equally important to increase policymakers' awareness of agroecology's role in sustainability.
- Agroecology as a practice should be encouraged in research. Showcasing agroecological practices through knowledge exchange among farmers and experimental fields can address financial barriers via policies and business models to promote environmental efforts.
- Co-creation allows the engagement of diverse stakeholders, especially research institutes. Advocating for co-creation benefits is crucial, emphasising the alignment of research proposal evaluation criteria with participatory approaches.
- Agroecology as a science can promote participatory approaches integrating farmer knowledge into scientific research. Agroecology as a scientific approach allows to gain a comprehensive understanding of the economic implications of agroecological practices. .

In summary, based on the analysis of capacity building activities collaboratively implemented in the ALL-Ready project and described in this report, several recommendations can be outlined to guarantee the successful establishment of the future network of agroecology LLs and RIs. As a matter of fact, it is crucial to involve a diverse range of stakeholders during the co-design phase of capacity building activities, ensuring a tailored, transparent collaboration and effective communication across all stakeholder types, with particular emphasis on engaging farmers. Facilitating cohesive cross-country cooperation and adopting a bottom-up approach will be pivotal for advancing agroecological transformation. Finally, maintaining network integrity through rigorous certification and multifaceted capacity building efforts will enable regular engagement of members.

1. Introduction

The ALL-Ready project's aim is to prepare a framework for a future network of Living Labs (LLs) and Research Infrastructures (RIs) that will enable the transition towards agroecology (AE) throughout Europe.

For actors to play a pivotal role in supporting AE transition, a specific set of skills and competences is crucial. Recognising this need, the ALL-Ready initiative has developed a comprehensive capacity building programme (CBP) tailored to support agroecology transition. This programme is specifically designed for LL and RI, which are integral components of the agroecology innovation ecosystem.

The overall objective of work package (WP) 5 is to prepare and initiate a CBP for the future network of LLs and RIs supporting agroecology transition. This CBP aimed to support the further development of, and exchange between existing and new LL and RI in agroecology across Europe. Rolling out the CBP will support the transition of European agri-food systems to agroecology by promoting agroecology and LL approaches.

This present report (deliverable D5.3 "Report on the capacity building validation activity and workshops") is provided as part of All-Ready's WP 5 ("Capacity Building") and aims to provide an overview of the activities and the results undertaken as part of following tasks:

- Task 5.1 – Scoping the capacity building programme
 - Sub-Task 5.1.1 – Specification of skills, competencies, and knowledge for key end-users
 - Sub-Task 5.1.2 – Defining the key end users and their needs
- Task 5.2 Prototyping and experimenting with the capacity building programme
- Task 5.3 – Implementing the capacity building programme
- Task 5.4 – Scaling up of the capacity building programme: communication and dissemination activities

The deliverable is structured in 7 different chapters:

- **Chapter 1 - Introduction** which provides an overview of the CBP activities aim and activities.
- **Chapter 2 - The capacity building programme** elucidates how the scope of the CBP was defined, providing insights into the key considerations and factors that influenced its design. The report explores the foundational decisions that shaped the CBP's focus and objectives, setting the stage for its subsequent development. This part offers an in-depth look at the prototyping phase, highlighting the collaborative efforts involved in creating the first version of the CBP with pilot network members (PNMs). It discusses the co-creation process, emphasising the active involvement of PNMs in shaping the content, structure, and goals of the CBP.
- **Chapter 3 - Implementation and testing of** delves into the practical aspects of the CBP, specifically focusing on the testing and implementation of the course "Understanding Living Lab Concepts and Co-creation", Systems Thinking Training, and the development of the Data Management Plan. The report provides an overview of the strategies employed, challenges encountered, and lessons learned during this crucial phase.

- **Chapter 4 - Additional capacity building items: field visits and learning** roundtables
- **Chapter 5 - Validation of the CBP** details the validation process of the CBP, culminating in a final workshop. It outlines how the CBP was presented to PNMs for validation, capturing their feedback and impressions. An overview of the feedback received from the PNMs is presented, shedding light on the programme's effectiveness and areas for improvement.
- **Chapter 6 - Recommendations for future** synthesises the insights gathered from partners of the ALL-Ready project, participants of regional workshops, and PNMs. Recommendations are provided on enhancing the CBP and expediting the transition towards AE.
- **Chapter 7 - Conclusions and Next Steps** offers a summary of the reflections on the performed CBP. The report concludes with a forward-looking perspective on the project's next steps and the continuous evolution of the CBP.

Living Labs & Research Infrastructures

Living labs have a long history, dating back to the 1990s. Since the establishment of ENoLL in 2006 under the Finnish Presidency of the Council of the EU, the LL community has grown in Europe and worldwide. The ENoLL living lab community now includes more than 160 active LLs, with 500+ historically labelled LLs working in different countries on 5 continents over a wide range of areas and offering different expertise and services.

ENoLL defines living labs as “user-centred, open innovation ecosystems based on systematic user co-creation approach, integrating research and innovation processes in real life communities and settings”.

Living labs play a crucial role in accelerating the adoption of sustainable practices by users and tailoring solutions to local conditions. The ALL-Ready project reinforces the link between living labs and research infrastructures, defining the latter as facilities that offer resources and services for research communities. These infrastructures, integral to the project, not only stimulate innovation but also extend their impact beyond research into education and public services. They encompass significant scientific equipment, collections, archives, computing systems, communication networks, and other distinctive research and innovation infrastructure components.

LLs and RIs have been identified as a tool to enable the transition towards AE within the ALL-Ready Project.

The draft proposal of the European Partnership under Horizon Europe "Accelerating farming systems transition: Agroecology Living Labs and Research Infrastructures" defines agroecology as the science of ecological processes applied to agricultural production systems, benefiting from the interplay between science, technology and traditional or indigenous knowledge by farmers and stakeholders in value chains. When applied to agroecology, living labs may be defined as transdisciplinary approaches which involve farmers, scientists, and other interested partners in the co-design and the monitoring and evaluation of new and existing agricultural practices and technologies on working landscapes to improve their effectiveness and early adoption. Agroecology Living Labs (AELs) work towards improving sustainability and resilience at the agroecosystem and landscape levels. As with other living labs, users – in this case, farmers – are at the centre.

Agroecology research infrastructures (AERI) serve as facilities offering resources and services to research communities engaged in agroecology research and innovation. They play a vital role in supporting the transition to agroecology by enabling scientists to observe, experiment, and forecast the redesign of agroecosystems and agri-food systems. Together, these infrastructures contribute to building a substantial body of scientific knowledge for the agroecology transition. LLs and RIs can

complement each other by facilitating ambitious experimentation at various scales, bridging the gap between practical applications and scientific inquiry. When employed collaboratively, LLs and RIs become powerful tools to accelerate the transition to agroecology.

Pilot Network of the ALL-Ready project

With the intention of preparing and initiating a CBP for the future network of LLs and RIs supporting agroecology transition, within the ALL-Ready project, the pilot network played a determinant role in providing feedback and suggestions on how to adapt the CBP to the agroecology context.

Launched in December 2021, the ALL-Ready PN comprises eight AELs, seven AERIs, and external advisory initiatives from the national network of Living Laboratories initiative on Agricultural Climate Solutions (Canada) and Guadalinfo (Spain).

PNMs actively contributed to the project by providing valuable feedback and suggestions for improving the CBP. The engagement aims to enhance the effectiveness of the CBP and address the specific needs and expectations of the network.

This deliverable serves as a comprehensive record of the CBP's journey within the ALL-Ready project, documenting the collaborative efforts, challenges faced, and the valuable feedback received from key stakeholders.

2. The capacity building programme

2.1 Scoping the capacity building programme

The process of developing the CBP consists of 5 steps: scoping, prototyping, co-design, implementation & testing.

The first step, aiming to define the scope of the CBP, was explained in the *D5.1 Report on mapped needs and the key end users of the capacity building programme*. The report provided the building blocks of the CPB to support the agroecology transition which is based on a **3-level approach**:

- Support the development of skills and knowledge of stakeholders involved in agroecology transition.
- Set up and management of agroecology living labs and research infrastructures.
- Set up and implementation of a European network of agroecology LLs and RIs.

The final CBP developed within WP5 of ALL-Ready is mainly targeted to the key end users of the second level: agroecology LLs and RIs. This is due to the nature of the project that put forward a strong focus on co-creation with the pilot network of WP3.

D5.1 described the work carried out under task T5.1 *Scoping the capacity building programme*, focusing on providing a framework for capacity building via the identification of key end users and their needs. Within this task, the **key end users** identified are:

- Research community
- Policymakers
- Farmers
- Consumers
- Intermediaries & value chain actors (e.g., advisors, living lab managers ...)
- Communication

The D5.2 *Skills and Competencies Framework* provides an overview of core competencies for accelerating agroecology transition through the development of LLs and RIs and their European networking. The deliverable offers valuable insights into the **competencies** necessary to facilitate the transition to agroecology among key end users throughout Europe, being identified as:

- Knowledge of AE research
- Agroecology practical farming skills and knowledge
- What agroecology is about
- Systems thinking and interdisciplinarity
- Understanding co-creation

In this context, the actual D5.3 *Report on the capacity building validation activity and workshops* focuses on the prototyping, the implementation, and the validation of the CBP itself within the ALL-Ready framework.

Building further on the described work in D5.1 and D5.2, a prototype CBP was developed including a CB materials database, three different CB training modules and additional capacity building methods such as field visits and roundtable learning within the pilot network (WP3). This prototype CBP was then validated and adapted within the pilot network in WP3. Finally, the validated outcomes were provided in (online) learning materials and recorded trainings.

However, as the context of agroecology transition is dynamic and complex, a CBP should be adapted and updated frequently. This developed CBP is not an endpoint.

2.2 Prototyping the capacity building programme

Following the conclusion of the scoping of the capacity building programme phase, the following new phase consisted of iterative steps of prototyping and testing. During the pilot network workshop organised by ÖMKi, ENoLL and EV ILVO on 4-5 July 2022 in Ghent, Belgium, the prototyping was addressed.

This phase encompassed the following actions: examining the existing capacity building materials related to the key competencies identified in the previous phase, determining which competencies required the development of a capacity building material prototype, and subsequently testing this prototype with a pilot group of end users for further enhancements.

The ultimate step, which is the implementation, consists of rolling out the programme to a wider audience.

During the meeting in Ghent, one specific session was dedicated to the prototyping and testing phase that included the following objectives:

- To present and validate the main 'needs for capacity building' that were identified during the first phase (scoping of the capacity building plan),
- To co-decide with the pilot network for which of these needs it was necessary to further develop capacity building material (prioritisation). More in detail, there was the need to identify the form in which the content had to be provided to the end user (training, guidelines, webinar, database, etc.)

The session titled "What competencies and skills can a European Network improve? Prototyping the capacity building programme", was organised as follows:

- Presentation of results of 'scoping of the capacity building plan'/ questions (15 min)
- Prioritisation exercise (15 min):

Content: What would be the most interesting content for capacity building material for the members in your LL/RI? Pilot network members had 3 voting sticky dots to prioritise main needs on a poster listing 'needs for capacity building'. Format: what would be the most interesting format to bring the content to the LL/RI members? Pilot network members had to draw a line from their sticky dot to a format of interest. (Figure 1 Results of prioritisation of content and format for developing capacity building material)

Figure 1 Results of prioritisation of content and format for developing capacity building material

During the session, participants discussed the availability of capacity building material for the 5 competencies listed below:

- Knowledge of AE research
- Agroecology practical farming skills and knowledge
- What agroecology is about
- Systems thinking and interdisciplinarity
- Understanding co-creation

Among these skills, at least one vote was cast for four of them, while 'systems thinking and interdisciplinarity' received no votes. Within the more general themes, only two specific topics received at least three votes: knowledge on socio-economic assessments in agroecology-related research (knowledge on AE research as the general theme) and setting up living labs (understanding co-creation as general theme).

The choice of the form of capacity building material largely depends on the content. For instance, for facilitation skills, there is a preference for a training course, whether it is conducted online or in person.

In contrast, for practical agroecology farming practices, participants favour demo events like farm visits, videos, and a bibliography database.

Participants indicated that, for 'knowledge on socio-economic assessments in agroecology-related research,' a peer-to-peer learning activity, such as an e-course, would be suitable. Regarding 'setting up living labs,' participants found a workshop, a library of best practices, and peer-to-peer learning activities to be appropriate. Regardless of the topic, peer-to-peer learning and other interactive methods are the most popular choices for capacity building materials.

In light of the findings from the session's activities, the following step consisted of gathering existing materials to support the development of capacity building formats. The WP5 team started the collection of pre-existing knowledge materials. Initially, this collection effort focused on materials from all internal ALL-Ready partners, but it was also extended to include other agroecology initiatives, identified through desktop research or connections from ALL-Ready partners' contacts. During the data collection phase, an Excel spreadsheet was used to gather the material's structure, a description, the intended audience, the language(s) in which it is available, the material's owner, and a hyperlink to the resource. The material has been gathered and collected in the database of training material available in Annex 5 Database of training material)

2.3 Co-design of the capacity building programme

The 3rd pilot network meeting (hybrid) was organised by ÖMKi between 21-23 November 2022. The event took place in Budapest, Hungary, but there was an opportunity to join online as well. The meeting was combined with a field visit to an organic farm (Csoroszlya Farm) at Szár, Hungary where members experienced how ÖMKi On-farm Living Lab operates from "farm to fork" and how participatory research between farmers-researchers-advisors-millers-bakers results in the development of a new value chain based on ancient cereals.

The session's objectives were the following:

- To present a first prototype of the capacity building programme and the gathered capacity building materials,
- To identify the gaps in the first prototype of the capacity building programme
- To co-decide with the pilot network:

How will be developed the training materials for the gaps in capacity building materials.

What is a feasible timeline for the delivery of the capacity building programme; and which validation process will be used for the CBP testing phase?

The session was organised in 4 sections:

- Introduction & Presentation on CBP Framework & Recap on the process
- Presenting the CBP: resources and gaps
- Interactive activity
- Validation of the CBP

Introduction, presentation on capacity building programme framework & recap on the process

Before the session started, an icebreaker was set up to energise the participants: the game BINGO. All participants were provided with a matrix, as shown in Figure 2 Bingo matrix, which contained various

questions to be posed to fellow participants. The objective was to engage in conversations with as many other participants as possible to fill in the answers on the matrix.

Find and write down the name of someone who...

B	I	N	G	O
Is in a sports group	Has lived in more than 4 countries	Find out someone's favourite hobby	Has a pet	Is left-handed
Someone who has run a (full, half) marathon	Can recommend a great novel	Has sung in a choir or sings professionally	Shares the same birthday month as you	Can speak more than 3 languages
Has hiked a famous trail / mountain	Find out someone's favourite plant		Find out someone's first live concert	Plays a musical instrument
Can recommend their favourite podcast	Has a vegetable garden	Has visited 5 out of 7 continents	Has met a celebrity	Has read 20+ books this year
Knows how to juggle	Has found a great new recipe	Is wearing a watch	Has more than 2 siblings	Knows the move to Macarena (bonus if they can demonstrate!)

Figure 2 Bingo matrix

Following the icebreaker activity, the group came back in plenary style for the first presentation of the workshop which was focused on the CBP framework & recap of the process. The presentation reviewed progress achieved to date under WP 5 to scope and prototype the CBP and included an overview of the extensive list and short list of competency areas as identified by the pilot network in previous workshops and interviews. This portion of the workshop was particularly valuable for the new members who recently joined the ALL-Ready pilot network and needed more context to better participate in the session.

Presenting the capacity building programme: resources and gaps

Following the recapitulation of the CBP, ILVO provided a more detailed overview of shortlisted competency areas and training topics that are to be addressed in the capacity building programme:

1. A common understanding of AE
2. Agroecology practical farming skills and knowledge
3. Knowledge of agroecology research
4. Systems thinking; and
5. Understanding co-creation

The participants were reminded of the previous agreement that was reached to focus solely on the level of agroecology living labs and research infrastructures for the capacity building programme, but that it was still possible to provide recommendations for the other two levels (agroecology in general and European network of agroecology LLs and RIs). ILVO also presented the results of a first round of data collection, which involved the ALL-Ready partners in the gathering of training materials and resources for all the above competency areas. The materials were presented to the pilot network in two ways:

- In an Excel spreadsheet format, which is the same format as was used for the data collection process (see Figure 3 Extract of the table of collected CB materials for an example with a limited extract). The Excel presents the format, a description of the material, the target audience, the language(s) in which it exists, the material owner and a link to the resource; and
- In a poster format which shows images of the collected materials to present the different formats of the materials (videos, reports, demo events, serious games, ...) and to make the poster more attractive. The posters are shown in Figures 4-8.

The collection of training materials and resources clearly demonstrated that there already exist many materials for the first 3 competency areas mentioned above, but that resources do not appear to be as accessible for the last two (systems thinking and co-creation). As such, a 3-pronged CPB prototype was proposed for the pilot network. This prototype aims to leverage and make effective use of existing resources while filling the gaps in training resource availability:

- Build a master database of training materials and resources which would cover each of the five competency areas and would present the materials in a user-friendly, highly customisable format using filters.
- Create a new training on systems thinking which would include a basic course in addition to one or more exercises adapted to agroecology cases of pilot network members; and
- Develop a 4-module course on understanding co-creation and living labs (see Figure 3 for the module details).

Agroecology practical farming skills and knowledge						
Format (video, e-course, database, etc)	Material description	Target audience	Language availability	Duration to view / review material (mins)	Material Owner (your organisation or another)	Link to resource
Video recording	Playlist on soil health practices in organic and agroecological farming (half in HU with subtitles, the other half in EN)	Farmers	HU, EN	av. 30 min/video	ÖMKi	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9SM8IQCrJM&list=PLAKR11cz4fO.jHAOn9RthurPXIXQMawzT
Video Recording	Playlist on proper seed treatment, storage and seed saving (half in HU with subtitles, the other half in EN)	Farmers, seed companies	HU, EN	av. 15 min/video	ÖMKi	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=8SbflQwwQ5A&list=PLAKR11cz4fOKg_j6rBBorMASbutedybf5
Video Recording	Videos consisting a wide range of organic and agroecological practices from crop production, animal husbandry, farm/food chain management etc.	Farmers, food chain companies	EN, FR, HU, IT, DE, ES, BG, FN, CZ, ET, LT	av. 15 min/video	Organic Farm Knowledge Platform	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCA7iMg-_4SxmWbxYQzfJEW
Publications	Downloadable publications on various organic farming practices and techniques from crop production, cover cropping, apiculture, viticulture to horticulture	Farmers	HU	90 min	ÖMKi	https://www.biokutatas.hu/hu/webshop/index/kiadvany/

Figure 3 Extract of the table of collected CB materials

Figure 4 Poster: Common understanding of agroecology

Figure 5 Poster: Practical farming skills

Figure 6 Poster: Knowledge of AE research

PhD course at the IFSA 2024

Develop new course: basic course + exercise adapted on AE case of PN members

Systems thinking

Figure 7 Poster: Systems thinking

Understanding Co-Creation

- Setting up living labs: governance models, evaluation of performance of LL
- Facilitation skills in co-creation settings

MODULE	DESCRIPTION
Module 1 – Set-up of LLs	- LL basics - governance model (w interaction/examples from LLs) - business model (w interaction/examples from LLs)
Module 2 - Management of LLs	- implementation plans (open innovation journeys) - panel management - pilot management
Module 3 - Co-creation and Experimentation	- Three Layer Model & Living Lab Integrative Process - Co-creation & Co-design - Real-life experimentation
Module 4 - Deep dive on geographical characteristics	Tentative

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Figure 8 Poster: Understanding Co-creation

Interactive activity

After the presentation of the first CBP prototype, an interactive activity was introduced to the participants. Participants were asked to give feedback on the materials collected (excel file and posters) (see Figure 4-8). Participants were asked to what extent materials were consistent with their needs and what could potentially be added. Regarding the training sessions on systems thinking and co-creation, participants were asked about their interest in these sessions and to what extent they could contribute to developing them..

A concise overview of the feedback and comments gathered in this activity is shown in the Annex 3 . The discussion however is further elaborated in the conclusion chapter of this report.

Validation of the capacity building programme

A final presentation also proposed a methodology for the **validation of the capacity building training sessions**. The participants were asked to provide their comments and feedback on a draft survey that would be used to evaluate training items.

Regarding the *co-designing the capacity building programme items*, participants approved the 3-pronged capacity building programme prototype:

- 1. Build a master database of training resources and materials** – The participants agreed on building an overall database as presented with smart filters and keywords. The database would be accessible to everyone because it will be put on the ALL-Ready website and the Virtual Lab platform. For the Virtual Lab, users should make a login to have access. Existing courses, whether in-person or online, can be added to the database, but it should be made clear who the audience is and whether there is a fee to take the course. Participants would also like the database to include literature and the latest best practices/methodologies regarding co-creation.
- 2. Create a new training session on Systems Thinking** - Participants agreed on creating new training on Systems thinking as presented.

- 3. Develop a multi-module course on understanding co-creation and living labs** - The PN agreed on creating new training sessions on understanding co-creation and living labs, but they recommended that the course should only cover the first 3 modules (Set-up of LLS, Management of LLS and Co-creation and Experimentation). Instead of having a fourth module on geographical specifications, it was recommended that geographical components should be treated as a transversal theme and should be incorporated, whenever applicable and using examples, in each of the three course modules. Participants were also interested in the course covering performance measurement in the living lab context. One participant indicated that the living lab methodology usually focuses on qualitative methods and that there is little information on quantitative aspects and research in the living lab context, especially concerning the data collection methods, projections, and use. It was recommended that this gap be considered when building the capacity building programme and that it might fit within the systems thinking portion.

Regarding the engagement of the pilot network in the further development and refinement of the capacity building programme, only one participant indicated that they wanted to support fine-tuning the training on systems thinking. No participants volunteered to support the fine-tuning of the co-creation training.

Participants approved the tentative timeline of activities regarding the delivery of the capacity building programme. They agreed to participate in the upcoming activities, but they preferred not to travel for the activity in February/March and instead to organise an online session. They indicated that they would attend the activity in June 2023 in person. They also agreed on the proposed validation process and survey. Pilot network members approved the use of a survey to validate the capacity building training sessions and offered some suggestions.

Pilot network members endorsed the implementation of a survey for validating the capacity building training sessions and shared some suggestions. The completed validation includes the following questions:

- Please indicate the level of overall usefulness of the capacity building items.
- Tell us about how the capacity building programme items have improved your knowledge of the content presented.
- Rate how the learning roundtable has helped you expand your knowledge in the following areas: Knowledge of AE research, Agroecology practical farming skills and knowledge, What agroecology is about, Systems thinking and interdisciplinarity, Understanding co-creation
- Rate how the Site Visit has helped you expand your knowledge in the following competencies: Knowledge of AE research, Agroecology practical farming skills and knowledge, What agroecology is about, Systems thinking and interdisciplinarity, Understanding co-creation
- What did you like most about the session?
- What recommendations do you have so we may improve?
- Would you recommend it to your colleagues (researchers, farmers, advisors, ...)? Why or why not?
- To what extent do you expect to use the information obtained through the capacity building programme items?
- What other topics would you like to hear/learn more about?

3. Implementation and testing of the capacity building programme

3.1 Collecting existing CB training materials in a database

Once the core competencies were identified, it was decided to first collect already existing training materials that can contribute to developing these competencies. Because many of the ALL-Ready partners are involved in agroecology research and practice, they were contacted in the first place to collect recent and useful training materials. Secondly, the pilot network members were asked to share training materials they have developed themselves or used in their living lab or research infrastructure. Finally, websites of related projects and networks about agroecology were screened to complete the database. The overview of the database is provided in an Excel file in Annex 5 Database of training material.

The database is structured around the format, description of material, some keywords, the language in which it appears, the duration, the owner, and the link to the resources.

The database is placed in the Virtual Research Environment (developed in WP6), the virtual space where members of the pilot network and the future network of LLs and RIs can add new materials.

Many training materials were found that concern a common understanding of agroecology, co-creation, and agroecology practices: especially YouTube videos, but also fact sheets, booklets, online courses, and MOOCs. For the competencies of systems thinking and setting up living labs, the materials found were rather scarce. Moreover, training materials specially adapted to agroecology were extremely scarce.

Therefore, it was decided to develop new materials for these two competencies. After agreeing with the pilot network members, EV ILVO developed an introductory training module on systems thinking and ENoLL created 3 modules on setting up, managing, and facilitating living labs.

3.2 The training course "Understanding Living Lab Concepts and Co-creation"

Within the ALL-Ready project, ENoLL has led the creation of an online training course titled "Understanding Living Lab Concepts and Co-creation". The workshop videos can be accessed on the ALL-Ready project website¹.

The training course consists of three modules of three hours each tackling the different steps to set up a living lab, their management, and the co-creation processes and facilitation techniques applied to living labs ecosystems. The modules consist of:

- Module 1 which offers participants an introduction to the fundamentals of living labs, including governance models and the business models associated with them.
- Module 2 that focused on the management of living labs.
- Module 3 that delves into frequently employed tools and methodologies during various stages of innovation management, along with facilitation techniques.

¹ Setting-up a capacity building programme for agroecology Living Labs and Research Infrastructures. <https://www.all-ready-project.eu/agroecology-living-labs-1-1.html>

A list of potential experts and trainers was initiated during the pilot network meeting in Ghent. The initial phase focused on identifying trainers associated with ALL-Ready partners, and in the following phase, the research was expanded to include trainers from affiliated organisations, projects, and desktop research involving all WP partners.

An Open call for trainers was published and shared by ENoLL to identify expert trainers to create and deliver a new course on understanding living lab concepts and co-creation. Applicants were requested to:

- Create the course content with oversight from the ENoLL team and other ALL-Ready project partners as needed.
- Schedule and coordinate the presentations/interventions of regional experts.
- Provide high-quality session/s in virtual and in-person environments.
- Deliver interactive exercise and provide live evaluation – a hands-on exercise for the participants to complete after their session/s.
- Participate in the post-course feedback session.
- Build and provide a list of at least 20 additional resources to be shared with participants as additional learning materials and to be used for the development of a database of training materials.

To apply, applicants were requested to send: their CV, a short video with an explanation of the proposal for the session and information on methodologies to be included in the lesson, examples of their experience as a practitioner, and the budget. ENoLL received six applications from various living labs.

The final selection was made based on factors such as the completeness of the application, speaking proficiency, coherence and comprehensiveness, depth of experience, and demonstrated expertise.

3.2.1 Module 1

On March 16, 2023, ENoLL, in collaboration with the ALL-Ready project, kicked off the first module of the online training session titled "Understanding Living Lab Concepts and Co-creation" This training session was specifically designed for members of the ALL-Ready pilot network, aiming to offer them a comprehensive understanding of the fundamental aspects of living labs, including governance models and the business models associated with them. During the training, the instructors shared valuable insights on the principles, methodologies, and tools essential for effectively implementing open innovation in agroecology through living labs.

18 pilot network members attended module 1 of the training course, consisting of 3 parts:

- Part 1: Living lab basics, long-term vision, and openness of innovation²
- Part 2: Governance models for living labs³
- Part 3: Business models of living labs⁴

Part 1 was conducted by Francesca Spagnoli, ENoLL Head of Capacity Building & Research. The focus of the presentation was the fundamental characteristics of setting up a living lab, the challenges, and

² Living Labs basics, Long-term vision and Openness of innovation. 16 March 2023
<https://vimeo.com/818318540/7bb8de0558>

³ Governance Models for Living Labs. 16 March 2023. <https://vimeo.com/818332357/a3fe2d3fcb>

⁴ Business Models of Living Labs. 16 March 2023. <https://vimeo.com/818369473/3c796817d3>

the open innovation journey. This section of the module centred on the fundamental aspects of living labs, highlighting their key elements, potential challenges, and essential insights. It provided an overview of the roles, duties, functioning, value generation, and value chain within living labs. Furthermore, it assisted participants in acquiring the knowledge necessary to establish long-term multi-stakeholder commitments and partnerships and in cultivating open innovation procedures and collaborations.

Fernando Vilariño, Associate Director Computer Vision Centre (CVC) and associate Professor Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona (UAB) gave an overview of the essential features of the governance models and their benefits. This part of Module 1 aimed to empower participants with the knowledge of creating a governance model that encompasses all actors within the quadruple helix for the long haul. The trainer supplied the canvas and tools necessary for shaping a governance model that participants could tailor to their specific circumstances, delineating the roles and responsibilities of each stakeholder involved.

To conclude the first Module, Juan Bertolin, General Manager, Fundació General Universitat Jaume, ESPAITEC Science and Technology Park presented the process of developing the business models by using the Business Models Canvas for Living Lab. This module explored comprehensively a diverse range of funding models for living labs, offering valuable insights into the effective acquisition of financial support from regional, national, and international sources. Moreover, it provided in-depth guidance on implementing strategies aimed at the establishment and long-term sustainability of living labs. In this context, participants acquired the knowledge and skills necessary to successfully secure funding, allocate resources judiciously for their living lab initiatives, and create a self-sustaining model for their living lab's operations.

Figure 9 Understanding Living Lab Concepts and Co-creation – Module 1

3.2.2 Module 2

As a continuation of the training course “Understanding Living Lab Concepts and Co-creation”, on April 12, 2023, ENoLL organised the second online training session that was attended by 14 pilot network members. Module 2 of the course centred on the Management of Living Labs and offered members of the ALL-Ready pilot network insights into various aspects, including the innovation management process of living labs, panel management, pilot management procedures, mapping canvas, and methodologies for assessing impact.

Dimitri Schuurman, Innovation Expert Methodology & Monitoring and Gilles Wuyts, Business analyst, IMEC guided participants through the overview of the living lab management roles and the innovation management process.

This part placed its emphasis on the process of mapping stakeholders, including the identification of pertinent users, and understanding their needs and expectations. It delved into the strategies for actively involving users in real-life scenarios, detailing the tools and methodologies employed in integrating users into innovation processes. Furthermore, the course guided participants in crafting a tangible plan of activities in accordance with the living lab methodology, encompassing various stages, SWOT analyses, and strategic planning for the future.

Pilot network members had the chance to choose and to test the Mapping Canvas and to discuss the several types of impact assessment.

Figure 10 Understanding Living Lab Concepts and Co-creation - Module 2

3.2.3 Module 3

ENoLL conducted the third training module⁵ of the "Understanding Living Lab Concepts and Co-Creation" training course on June 15, 2023, in Montpellier, France, during the 3rd pilot network meeting. This session, titled "Living Lab Model, Real-life Experimentation & Facilitation Techniques," was facilitated by trainers Dimitri Schuurman & Gilles Wuyts from IMEC. It is an integral part of the broader capacity building programme for agroecology living labs developed within the scope of ALL-Ready.

26 participants attended the workshop and were introduced to commonly utilised tools and methods in each phase of innovation management, and they received insights into facilitation techniques designed to gather users perspectives and needs within the context of agroecology.

The training tackled the following topics:

- The importance of the living lab model in fostering innovation and sustainable practices, particularly in the agroecology domain.
- The three layers of the living lab model: desirability, feasibility, and viability.
- The interrelation between these layers and their significance in the innovation process.
- Commonly used tools and methods in each phase of innovation management.

⁵ Module 3: Understanding Living Lab Concepts and Co-creation. 15 June 2023. <https://www.all-ready-project.eu/agroecology-living-labs-1-1/module-3.html>

- Showcasing of specific agroecology examples and case studies to highlight the application of co-creation and real-life experimentation in sustainable farming systems.
- Introduction to multiple facilitation techniques for capturing user insights and needs in agroecology projects and problem-solving to agroecological challenges.
- Group discussion and exercises: participants split into groups to practice some of the techniques shown in role-playing activities to practice and apply facilitation techniques, focusing on agroecology-specific scenarios and live interaction.

The workshop was designed in two parts: in the first part, the trainers explained the theoretical framework of the LL concept, the common tools, and methods in each phase of innovation management. In addition, specific agroecology examples and case studies were highlighted and discussed with the participants. In the second part, attendees were divided into groups to engage in role-playing activities, practicing and applying facilitation techniques. The emphasis was on agroecology-specific scenarios and real-time interactions.

Finally, drawing from their experiences within the pilot network, members proposed recommendations for the prospective European Network, encompassing aspects such as operations, structure, governance, and scalability.

Following the conclusion of the third training session, a dedicated portion was allocated to discussing areas for improvement in the CBP. ENoLL introduced a new segment of the discussion to collaboratively identify topics for the last workshop with the Project Network Managers (PNMs), resulting in the following themes:

- Training on stakeholder engagement
- Training on setting up the living lab – the operational phase
- Workshop with peer-to-peer consulting among LL & LH
- Discussion to identify the connection between the RIS and LLs and how to strengthen the collaboration

Taking in consideration this feedback and the comments received from the feedback forms completed by the participants after the training, the validation workshop was designed as explained in Chapter 5.

Figure 11 Understanding Living Lab Concepts and Co-creation - Module 3

3.3 Systems thinking module

This training module was built on a former training on systems thinking developed by ILVO for mapping the system in various agrifood contexts with different stakeholder groups. It was used and developed through workshops with the hemp value chain sector, the pig value chain sector, the agroecology living lab LLAEBIO and the Ministry of Agriculture. The training was adapted to agroecology by including examples of agroecology, by including questions such as why systems thinking is an important competency for agroecology transition and why systems thinking is an important competency for agroecology living labs and research infrastructures. Input on actual ongoing agroecology cases was solicited from the pilot network members beforehand to include in the systems thinking exercises.

The aim of the training on systems thinking is to help participants to understand how systems thinking can support them in their daily work.

This is achieved by providing:

- An introduction on systems thinking: what does systems thinking involve and when should we use systems thinking?
- To understand why systems thinking is an important competency for agroecology transition
- To understand why systems thinking is an important competency for agroecology living labs and research infrastructures
- To have an introduction and first exercise with two tools for systems thinking (causal loop diagrams, actor mapping)

The target public of the training includes researchers in agroecology transition and facilitators of agroecology living labs.

To introduce systems thinking and to give a sense of what systems thinking is about, a group energiser was presented. The general introduction on systems thinking included many examples on agroecology and agriculture to make the direct link with the field of interest of the participants in the room. Some participants were already more familiar than others with systems thinking. Interaction was sufficiently addressed by involving them in the introductory part by asking to give examples based on their daily experiences in the field/living lab/research: «what is a wicked problem », «what is a system, what are the boundaries», etc.

Two cases from the participants were brought in to use in the exercises on systems thinking tools. One was used because of the overall recognition of the problem (drought and water scarcity) and the multi-level approach, the other one was not used, because of a lack of time. Participants were invited to think about the variables they would use in applying the causal loop diagram tool and the stakeholders they would invite to the workshop for applying the tool.

A final moment of discussion (before the evaluation) was preserved for reflecting on the use of systems thinking for agroecology living labs and research infrastructures: Participants asked how such tools can be applied at the farm level. It was explained that the causal loop diagram can be used at many levels, including farm level (system boundaries). It can be useful to apply with farmers to get a full understanding of a complex issue they are confronted with, e.g. what variables impact their income; how can they better define their income.

Although a causal loop diagram doesn't provide real solutions, it was recognised by the participants that a causal loop diagram can be used in a living lab to better understand what issues they first need to address and what are big and smaller issues. It's a tool to integrate different perspectives to get a full understanding of the system. This tool can be used as an entry point to identify levers for change in the system.

Another participant indicated that this is a useful exercise to map the variables and relations between these variables to develop a computerised model to gain more insight into system dynamics and scenario modelling.

Figure 12 Systems Thinking training

4. Additional capacity building items: field visits and learning roundtables

Besides building new CB items, additional capacity building trainings were organised within the pilot network meetings. Field visits are interesting capacity building items because they provide first-hand experiences in agroecology practices, they strengthen observation and perception skills, they provoke discussions from the different perspectives on agroecology in general and they develop social skills.

The learning roundtables were meant to stimulate peer to peer learning on competencies important for agroecology transition in LLs and RIs. The learning roundtables fostered the exchange of thoughts and concepts about the general understanding of agroecology, but also on understanding how co-creation can work.

The pilot network meetings that were organised physically in Ghent, Budapest and Montpellier were ideal moments to explore these capacity building methods.

4.1 The Field Visits

4.1.1 Demonstration at the experimental platform in Hansbeke

During the second day of the pilot network meeting in Ghent (Belgium), a field visit was organised to Hansbeke. This field visit was part of the yearly 'Demonstration Day on the Experimental Platform for agroecology in Hansbeke'⁶ (Belgium). The experimental platform for agroecology conducts research on agroecological practices in a real-life context (farm of 60ha). Its objective is to optimise agroecological practices based on scientific observations in practical situations and to contribute to build and disseminating knowledge on agroecological practices to stimulate wider implementation. The Agroecology experimental platform in Hansbeke is a collaboration between ILVO (a research centre), organic grower Felix de Bousies and Alain Peeters as farm advisor on agroecology and researcher.

The demonstration event was aimed at all farmers, contractors, advisers, policymakers, and teachers who want to learn how to work on agroecology with particular focus on soil quality with free nitrogen and carbon from the air. The demonstration event contained both informal and formal moments to exchange knowledge. Therefore, the event was ideal to learn about agroecology in general, agroecology practices and agroecology research. The event started with a plenary session to give a general introduction on the platform and the farm. Translation was foreseen for the pilot network members. After the plenary session, there was a guided tour with different stops. At each stop, a partner of the platform or a researcher from ILVO demonstrated a particular experiment. The following topics were included in the guided tour:

- Cooperation regarding on-farm composting
- Grass clover and soil profile pit
- Agroforestry
- Intercropping with cereals
- Old grain varieties
- Chickpeas

After the guided tour in the fields, a networking moment was foreseen as closure of the event. Pilot network members perceived the field visit as one of the highlights of the 2-day pilot network meeting.

⁶ Over Proefplatform - PPAE Hansbeke. <https://www.ppaehansbeke.be/en/about>

Participants indicated that these demonstrations should be included in each pilot network meeting.

Figure 13 Experimental platform for agroecology in Hansbeke

Figure 14 EV ILVO researchers demonstrating results of on farm experiments

4.1.2 Field visit to Csoroszlya Farm

A following field visit was organised in the pilot network meeting in Budapest in November 2022 to an organic farm (Csoroszlya Farm) in Szár, Hungary. It offered attendees a first-hand opportunity to observe the operational dynamics of ÖMKi On-farm Living Lab, spanning the entire process from the farm to the dining table. During this visit, participants gained insight into how collaborative research involving farmers, researchers, advisors, millers, and bakers culminates in the creation of a novel value

chain centred on heritage grains. The farmer of Csoroszlya Farm explained about the selection of good grain varieties adapted to the climate and soil. He stressed the importance of ecological farming for achieving high-quality grain (and other products). To continue the quality of the grain, he bought a high-quality stone mill from France to grind the grain himself and to provide high quality flowers to bakeries in the capital Budapest. For the farmer, values such as autonomy, quality, transparency, sustainability, and innovation are important. Although the farmer did not speak about agroecology as such, it was clear that he was implementing various agroecology practices and trying to implement agroecological principles in the whole value chain from cultivating wheat up to baking the bread.

Figure 15 Field visit at the Csoroszlya Farm

4.1.3 Field visit to the Occitanum Living Lab

The field visit in the pilot network meeting in Montpellier was meant to explore one of Occitanum's Open Labs. Occitanum comprises a network of 13 living labs situated in diverse pedo-climatic and production locations throughout the Occitanie Region. These application-oriented laboratories serve as a meeting ground for a wide array of local and regional stakeholders, encompassing farming communities, local government bodies, agricultural development organisations, AgTech companies, citizens, as well as researchers, engineers, technicians, and academics. Together, they collaborate on the creation of pioneering initiatives tailored to various agricultural systems, such as orcharding, beekeeping, livestock farming, crop cultivation, viticulture, and horticulture, in addition to local food systems.

Participants travelled to Mas Numérique where the Open Lab VITI is located in order to see how the co-creation services with farmers and firms are organised.

This visit allowed them to gain first-hand experience with the testing and implementation of digital tools in the context of agroecology, particularly in the field of viticulture by exploring:

- Mas Numérique digital farm: it serves as a showcase for cutting-edge digital technologies in the field of wine cultivation and offers a training resource for students and professionals in the industry.

- Agrotic Mobilab: to raise awareness among farmers on ways to apply technology in agriculture.

Figure 16 Field visit to Las Mas Numérique

4.2 Learning Roundtables

4.2.1 Learning round table on best practices for co-creation and stakeholder engagement

The objective of this activity was to stimulate peer-to-peer learning on co-creation and stakeholder engagement by 1) sharing inspiring examples of approaches for co-creation and stakeholder engagement and 2) by peer consultation on challenges related to co-creation and stakeholder engagement. More specifically, Rebecca Swinn from Innovative Farmers and Chris McPhee from AAFC (Agriculture and Agri Food Canada) presented the co-creation practices used in their LLs. Then, the members were divided into two groups to share problems and challenges that they face in relation to co-creation and stakeholders involvement, and then to find solutions together to the identified problems.

This activity was organised by the WP3 team of ALL-Ready, together with the two pilot network members AAFC and Innovative Farmers. Facilitation was done by Korinna Varga (ÖMKi) and May Hobeika (Ecologic). Facilitators were supported by two pilot members (Chris McPhee and Rebecca Swinn) as lead peers in the breakout groups.

The lack of motivation of stakeholders, long-term participation of end-users, the differing needs and expectations of researchers and farmers and the technical and time-related constraints were highlighted as main problems faced during co-creation and stakeholder engagement. As solutions, the groups found that it is necessary to clearly formulate, communicate and repeat information on shared benefits, expectations of the stakeholders and the added value of the cooperation; regular evaluation might help to address the issues.

4.2.2 Learning Roundtable: Co-creation tools to address the gap between the needs of scientists and farmers

The session was also organised by the WP3 team of ALL-Ready, together with a small task force of the pilot network on Learning Roundtables (comprised of AAFC, Innovative Farmers, and CarbonFarm). During breakout sessions, facilitation was done by Korinna Varga (ÖMKi), Chris McPhee (AAFC) and Ana Allamand (Soil Association). Facilitators were supported by notetakers from ÖMKi (Valéria Csonka), Ecologic (May Hobeika) and ILVO (Sylvie Fosselle).

The aims were threefold:

- to inform the members about three practical tools for co-creation and stakeholder engagement to address the gap between scientists and farmers that they can use in their own LL/RI;
- to learn about the implementation and use of these tools through situational exercises;
- to reflect on the usefulness of the tools.

The learning roundtable session was organised following the following agenda:

- Session objective, method, exercise (2 min)
- Presentation of LIAISON co-creation tools (20 min)
- Round 1: Situational exercises in groups using the 3 co-creation tools (50 min)
- Round 2: Situational exercises in groups using the 3 co-creation tools (50 min)
- Presenting the results of the group work and reflections (20 min)

Ana Allamand from Innovative Farmers presented the LIAISON co-creation toolkit focusing on three tools:

- Ground Rules: Identification of opportunities and challenges of agreement-based cooperation,
- Needs Register: Recording stakeholders needs & assessing responsiveness
- Speed boat: Clarifying and agreeing on the main idea together with the practices used in their LLs.

Then, the members were grouped into three groups, each having different scenarios. In each group, there was one facilitator and one notetaker, and members were randomly assigned to groups where each of them impersonated a particular LL/RI actor of their choosing (farmers, researcher, advisor, policymaker etc.). After having discussed and clarified the scenarios, the task was the same in all groups: members had to use the co-creation tool assigned to their group with the help of the facilitators to address the given scenario.

After 50 minutes, the members switched groups (facilitators stayed) and repeated the task but now using another co-creation tool. In this way, all members had the opportunity to try out at least two co-creation tools.

The "Co-creation tools for bridging the gap between scientists and farmers" session constituted the second segment of the learning roundtable series, building on the outcomes of the preceding session which focused on "Best practices for co-creation and stakeholder engagement." This session had a specific focus on disseminating information about three distinct co-creation tools and, notably, providing instruction to members on how to apply and utilise these tools through role-playing exercises. The collaborative exercises assisted members in understanding how to establish shared objectives, evaluate and gather input from various stakeholders, and establish cooperation guidelines for situations where circumstances change, and different stakeholders are involved. It is anticipated that these tools will prove valuable in assisting members in addressing similar challenges within their own living labs and research infrastructures.

5. Validation of the CBP

The validation of the CBP occurred through two primary methods: participants were invited to provide their feedback via surveys, and a concluding workshop was conducted. The section below explains the outcomes of the different methodologies.

5.1 Summary of the Surveys

As shown in Graph 1, the post-event survey results for the CBP series showed that the three Modules were very useful and extremely useful for more than 30% of the participants. In fact, each of the three modules received a high usefulness score which are shown in Graph 1.

Graph 1 Overview of the feedback on the three modules

Improvement of the knowledge

It is interesting to notice that in the three modules and the systems thinking training, attendees' scores vary notably depending on the competence. In fact, while the competences "What agroecology is about" and "Knowledge on agroecology Research" do not show a particular level of improvement, the knowledge of "agroecology farming practices" has improved a little and moderately for 10% of the respondents. On the other hand, the knowledge of "Systems thinking" and "Understanding Co-creation" improved significantly and very significantly for 50% of the respondents as seen in Graph 2. These results can be explained by considering that in the first phase of the design of the CBP, the need to focus the CBP on "Systems thinking" and "Understanding Co-creation" was highlighted.

Graph 2 Knowledge improved on Systems thinking and Co-creation

Systems thinking surveys

The systems thinking training received overall positive feedback, with an average of 27,3% of participants who found the training “very useful” and 24,3% of participants who considered it “extremely useful” (Graph 3).

3. Please indicate the level of overall usefulness for each training module session:

Graph 3 Level of usefulness of the systems thinking training

As seen in Graph 4, 18,2% of participants significantly improved their knowledge on systems thinking and interdisciplinarity and 27.3% improved “very significantly” their knowledge in this area.

5. Rate how the training module has helped you expand your knowledge in the following areas:

Graph 4 Score on the training module Systems thinking

A more comprehensive overview of the feedback received is described in Annex 2 post-workshop survey overview .

5.2 Validation workshop

On September 22, 2023, during the Open Living Labs Days, held in Barcelona, ENoLL hosted the final CBP workshop. Titled "capacity building for agroecology," this session represented the last phase in the development of a CBP tailored for agroecology living labs and research infrastructures. The workshop's primary objective was to bring together members of the ALL-Ready pilot network, offering them the opportunity to assess the progress made in the CBP conducted thus far and to gather valuable insights for shaping the programme's future direction. Additionally, this workshop facilitated the exchange of experiences among pilot network members through peer-to-peer exchange, with a particular focus on specific aspects of living lab and research infrastructure management.

As part of the post-workshop survey questions, it was requested to suggest discussion topics for this workshop. The main suggestions are summarised below:

- Tools to keep stakeholders involved in a LL and tools to onboard a new member of a LL if the LL has already been running for a while
- More facilitating techniques adapted to agroecology LLs
- Evaluation and monitoring (with indicators) of LL processes
- Panel management
- More time for practising the tools , less frontal presentation and more group discussions
- Space for exchange without imposed programme

To design the last workshop programme and activities, the WP5 team gathered the suggestions received through the open discussion that was held during the pilot network meeting in Montpellier. The suggestions shared were the following:

- Training on stakeholder engagement
- Training on setting up the living lab – the operational phase
- Workshop with peer-to-peer consulting among LLs & LHs
- Discussion to identify connections between research infrastructures and LLs and how to strengthen the collaboration

Taking into consideration these ideas and these suggestions, the last workshop was organised; the agenda is provided in the Annex 4.

The outcomes of the group discussion are the following:

Topic: Examine a particular facilitation tool/technique and get recommendations for applicability in local context.

Facilitation techniques should remain simple. Group discussions need to be completely guided, without the need for writing. Ideally, the facilitator should be a familiar, respected, and trusted figure for the participants, with a good rapport. Facilitators should possess the necessary technical knowledge. The level of engagement should be tailored according to the audience and the type of stakeholders involved. When dealing with policymakers, direct communication is essential.

Topic: how to better adapt the CB to AE

Participants recommended trying out the CBP and soliciting ongoing feedback. The significance of providing facilitation training was emphasised to effectively engage stakeholders and prepare facilitators to handle various situations with flexibility. Pilot network members shared the importance of facilitators possessing technical knowledge in the subject matter. Regarding the monitoring and evaluation framework, participants stressed the need for a standardised framework that can later be customised.

One group discussed the business models and how to better adapt them to the topic of Agroecology. The definition of products should be expanded to encompass not only the economic dimension but also the environmental and social aspects. Using a "flourishing business model canvas" was suggested, which serves as an effective initial approach. There is a recognised requirement to broaden the involvement of stakeholders and examine the various additional values so that other participants can contribute a more diverse range of resources, beyond mere financial gain.

Topic: How do you measure and evaluate the impact of your LL/RI? What are the KPIs, how do you track success, etc. What are some best practices or lessons learned for long-term sustainability (operational, financial, etc.) of your LL/RI?

Participants shared that there exists a multitude of key performance indicators (KPIs) for measurement, yet some elements prove difficult to quantify. For example, evaluating factors such as trust-building can be elusive. It is of utmost importance to oversee different tracks, the processes within living labs, and their resulting outcomes. The integration of acquired lessons is indispensable. It is critical to diversify funding sources, ensuring that resources do not overly rely on a single project. A well-defined leadership framework is a prerequisite, and adaptability stands as a cornerstone.

Topic: How do you organise field visits? How do you engage stakeholders during field visits (what do you do)? What constitutes a good/successful field visit and why? How would you integrate the concepts/methodologies or tools/techniques in the field visit?

Field visits offer a unique chance to unite diverse groups, ranging from marketing professionals to farmers and even policymakers who may not typically engage in conversations.

Field visits provide a platform to showcase the living lab's results to the public, bridging the gap between research and the wider community. Repeating field visits can be intriguing, but timing is critical since the outcomes often hinge on the season. To make field visits more effective, the inclusion of an expert facilitator is essential, ensuring active engagement of participants.

Social scientists can play a pivotal role in orchestrating these visits and fostering meaningful interactions among the participants.

Topic: How do you make sure that stakeholders are engaged in your LL/RI? How do you retain them (what are the incentives you use)?

Establishing trust is a time-consuming yet indispensable process for achieving impact and securing the involvement of stakeholders. This can primarily be achieved through telephone communication, particularly at the local level. Identifying opportunities for people to become better acquainted is crucial. It is vital to have a consistent and well-known figure among stakeholders, someone they have been familiar with for an extended period and can reach out to at any time. Identifying a shared core value is the linchpin for aligning stakeholders' interests and ensuring their active participation.

The last workshop was considered by 22.2% of participants as “moderately useful” and by 44.4% as “extremely useful” (Graph 5). This positive feedback highlights how well the content aligns with the needs and expectations of the participants, reinforcing the significant impact of the series in offering valuable insights and knowledge. This feedback further validates the programme's success in delivering pertinent and meaningful information, thereby contributing to the programme's overall effectiveness as a valuable platform for learning and engagement.

Graph 5 Feedback from the validation workshop

6. Recommendations for future capacity building

Besides developing a CBP focused on agroecology LLs and RIs, recommendations were formulated for initiating a CBP at the first level, to support the development of skills and knowledge of stakeholders involved in agroecology transition. The section below provides an overview of the recommendations gathered in two main ways:

- From the analysis of the outcomes of four regional workshops conducted collaboratively by WP4 and WP5 in Seville, Budapest, Frankfurt, and Helsinki. The workshops involved diverse participants from multiple countries, fostering discussions on competencies, regional gaps, and the role of local actors in supporting development.
- In WP4, interviews were carried out within the ALL-Ready consortium. As outcome of the interviews, recommendations on how to improve and apply the CBP were gathered.

6.1 Recommendations for capacity building on agroecology in general in the different regions

D5.1 Report on mapped needs and the key end users of the capacity building programme and D5.2 Skills and Competencies Framework provide an overview of needs for capacity building to foster agroecology transition in general, as well as capacity building specifically for LL/RIs and networks of LL/RIs. While D5.1 approaches capacity building very broadly as skills, instincts, abilities, processes, and resources needed by LLs, RIs, networks of LLs and RIs, and the stakeholders involved in them, D5.2 focuses specifically on **competencies (skills and knowledge)** needed by stakeholders involved in LL/RI and the network of LL/RI to engage in agroecology transition. Together with the pilot network members, gaps were identified in skills and competencies needed to support them in their daily work of running an agroecology LL/RI. To get a broader view of missing skills and knowledge throughout Europe, we followed a region-based approach to provide more general recommendations on competencies that need further development to foster agroecology transition. Therefore, in Europe, four regional workshops have been conducted.

The workshops were organised as a collaboration between WP4 and WP5 and took place on the 11th of May in Seville (Spain), the 12th of May in Budapest (Hungary), the 22nd of June in Frankfurt (Germany), and the 29th of September in Helsinki (Finland) and were organised by the Thünen Institute of Farm Economics (Frankfurt), LIFEWATCH Eric (Seville), ÖMKI (Budapest), Biosense Institute, Ecologic Institute, University of Oulu (Helsinki), ILVO, ENoLL, and INRAE. All workshops were held in a hybrid format and brought together participants from Austria, Belgium, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Latvia, Portugal, Serbia, Slovakia, Spain, Denmark, Estonia, and Finland. Participants represented a wide range of living labs and other open innovation arrangements, research infrastructures, and funding organisations. During the main part of the workshop, the participants worked in small groups to discuss topics, themes, and issues that the future network of agroecology living labs and research infrastructures should address. Debates revolved around diverse needs for long-term running of a European network on agroecology LL and RIs. During a one-hour timeslot, participants focused on discussing regional gaps in competencies and the role of local actors in supporting the development of competencies. To initiate the discussion on capacity building, the WP5 lead (ENoLL) or co-lead (EV ILVO) presented 5 key competencies and asked participants to what extent each of these competencies was sufficiently developed among different stakeholder groups in the region. These 5 key competencies were identified by the pilot network as key in supporting agroecology transition. Depending on the number of people in each group, some actually scored to what extent each of these competencies was

developed among farmers, researchers, education, advisory services, agribusiness, and living labs (see picture). In other groups, there was a more general discussion on the development of some or all competencies, without giving scores to each of the stakeholder groups.

To what extent is this competence developed among the following stakeholder groups in your region?

	<i>Not developed at all</i>	<i>Very well developed</i>
Farmers	1	10
Research	1	10
<u>Education</u>	1	10
<u>Advisory services</u>	1	10
<u>Agribusiness</u>	1	10
Living labs	1	10

Figure 17 Development level of the competences among the stakeholders

In what follows, some key recommendations are listed for each of the five key competences. Due to the relatively small number of participants in the workshops (17 participants in Budapest, 18 participants in Seville, 15 participants in Frankfurt, and 16 participants in Helsinki), the results do not allow conclusions on regional differences.

Systems thinking

Systems thinking is about cyclical thinking and understanding systems as the dynamics and relationships between the components that make up a greater whole. If one element is broken or moved, then it will affect the entire system. A major goal of systems thinking is to understand the flows, relationships, and behaviour of parts within a system to enable the potential for change while avoiding unintended consequences and behaviours. Systems thinking is needed to fully grasp path dependencies and lock-ins and to assess both short- and long-term consequences of the complex challenges of our European agrifood systems. It supports developing the capacity to understand and embrace the diversity in perspectives of all stakeholders involved and moving towards a shared understanding of the problem. During the systems thinking workshops, it was mentioned that systems thinking should be further supported by the future Agroecology partnership. As there is another partnership on sustainable food systems, these activities could be jointly organised. There was no clear target group identified, although researchers were mentioned as key as they often are experts in a specific domain, which might hamper seeing the connections with other elements in the system of interest. Furthermore, participants stated that policy instruments as well as the future network of living labs should stimulate systems thinking among all stakeholders.

Agroecology as a concept

Agroecology as a concept is more known in some countries or regions compared to others. Whereas in some countries, emphasis is still mainly on developing organic farming, for example in Denmark and

Estonia, other countries or regions focus on developing agroecology. Participants agree that the concept is mainly introduced by research and/or social movements. However, they also agree that policymakers are often insufficiently aware of the concept and its potential in supporting transition to sustainable farm and food systems. As policymakers are the ones integrating the principles into national and local policies, efforts should be made to inform them and increase their awareness of the concept. Highlighting inspiring examples of how municipalities or regions stimulate agroecology was mentioned as a major step in that direction.

Farmers do apply agroecological practices without being aware of the concept of agroecology. It was mentioned that agroecology should be integrated more into education (courses, degrees), from primary school to universities, and into advisory services. Other participants emphasised the importance of putting efforts into developing a general understanding of agroecology (in all languages) and of developing a widely accepted narrative (sustainable development goals), instead of targeting particular stakeholder groups in each country separately.

During one of the workshops, one participant realised that his understanding of 'what is agroecology' was quite different from the definition as presented by the future partnership on agroecology. He was quite stunned, and he did not feel comfortable to engage in the further discussion without reading and learning more about the 'European definition of agroecology'. This anecdote shows that different definitions of agroecology are still in place. This might also explain to some extent why scores given by the participants were very diverse (see picture below).

Figure 18 Agroecology as a concept

Agroecology in practice

Although participants indicated that agroecological practices are to some extent applied in the field., they agreed that some important barriers prevent wider implementation. One of the barriers mentioned was a lack of knowledge. It was recommended to introduce experimental fields in a region to demonstrate the results of agroecological practices to farmers. Learning from other farmers was perceived as highly effective in stimulating adoption. One participant particularly mentioned the knowledge exchange between organic and conventional farmers. Highlighting successful implementation on other farms might promote adoption by other farmers. Besides local demonstrations, it was also mentioned that the exchange of knowledge beyond across regional borders might be remarkably interesting to gain more insight into how other farmers in other regions deal with similar problems (e.g., drought, climate change). Besides knowledge, the economic situation of farms was mentioned as an important barrier to implementing agroecological practices. Financial problems force farmers sometimes to survive from one year to another, which prevents them from developing a long-term vision and engaging in agroecology transition. Implementing agroecology in practice also needs new business models to reward farmers for their efforts to produce in a more environmental friendly manner. Also, environmental measures promoted by the government are not implemented because rewards are insufficient. Participants mentioned the added value of setting up living labs in to bring stakeholders together to develop business models inspired by agroecological principles (participatory guarantee schemes, community supported agriculture, etc.). Also, research might support agroecology in practice by developing more insights about the environmental impact of agroecological practices.

Co-creation

Participants indicated that there is still a pronounced tendency to work as individuals instead of together. The approach of co-creation of innovation needs to be introduced/practiced at an early age during formal education to show the advantages of this approach to develop innovation and research. This competency was perceived as closely related to systems thinking since by stimulating co-creation, systems thinking is stimulated as well. According to some participants, research institutes are best placed to set up co-creation initiatives, so they were mentioned as a key target group for developing skills on co-creation approaches. However, other stakeholders should be aware of the benefits of co-creation to get them engaged in living labs. Some of the researchers that participated in the workshops perceived some difficulties in putting this into practice. Co-creation ideally includes end-users from the start. However, this is difficult to align with the way research proposals are currently developed. It is difficult to include stakeholders from the start when a research proposal needs to be developed, as budget comes only after the proposal has been approved. The consequence is that researchers write proposals from their perception of research needs.

Agroecology as a science

Agroecology as a science is based on participatory approaches in which close collaboration between farmers and researchers allows integration of expert knowledge with tacit knowledge of the farmers. Agroecology as a scientific approach is perceived as important to get a thorough understanding of economic impact of agroecological practices to support farmers in decision making. Research infrastructures might have an added value here in developing an open database with data on the impact and effectiveness of agroecological practices. Investing in systems thinking and co-creation for researchers is believed to be a leverage for developing agroecology as a scientific approach. Another leverage might be to develop other KPI's to evaluate research. Publications are not the main

outcome/output of participatory research processes. Funding bodies should re-evaluate their approach for evaluating research proposals based on a participatory approach.

6.2 Recommendations for capacity building on a European network level

In the framework of WP4 of the ALL-Ready project, a series of interviews were undertaken within the ALL-Ready consortium. These interviews were conducted with the purpose of gathering valuable insights and perspectives. The outcomes of these interviews proved instrumental in formulating comprehensive recommendations aimed at improving and effectively implementing the CBP of the ALL-Ready project.

Engagement of stakeholders

The significance of involving various stakeholders was highlighted, for example researchers and land use managers for enhancing soil health and sustainable land management. It is necessary to acknowledge the challenge of maintaining participant motivation and tailored approaches could overcome it. The emphasis is on collaboration, transparency, and stakeholder engagement in addressing complex issues, with open access to research results. Effective communication is crucial to make research findings accessible to policymakers and other users. Additionally, involving farmers in data collection and analysis is vital for improving project outcomes, particularly in assessing crop yields.

Cross-regional collaboration

Regional exchange was highlighted as very important to foster cross-country cooperation and knowledge exchange, which in turn can drive innovation and policy development within multi-actor engagement. The emphasis is on creating opportunities for a unified voice in AE transition, involving all EU countries and grassroots farmer organisations. Facilitating collaboration and knowledge exchange among diverse networks places farmers and their associations at the centre, maintaining a clear bottom-up approach.

Funding support

Many respondents advise securing funding and expanding network reach through larger networks while improving communication and dissemination efforts. Expanding the network, promoting collaborative engagement, and sharing resources are crucial for increasing effectiveness and reach. To ensure financial stability and reduce reliance on public funds, diversifying funding sources is crucial.

Certification and quality assessment

Rigorous certification and quality assessment are vital to preserve the integrity of the living lab network and ensure genuine contributors to open innovation. In agroecosystem living lab research, capacity building and a multifaceted approach are essential, involving joint meetings, knowledge exchange, and formal agreements among relevant organisations and countries. Regular engagement with members to understand their expectations and needs is critical for network effectiveness and adaptation of capacity building efforts.

7. Conclusion

The CBP stands as a cornerstone of the ALL-Ready project, representing a substantial influence on transition towards agroecology. This comprehensive report on capacity building meticulously examines each item delivered through the CBP by the ALL-Ready project. It includes a thorough account of both positive outcomes and constructive feedback garnered from the implemented activities.

The pivotal role played by the pilot network members cannot be overstated, as they were instrumental in defining, adapting, and soliciting suggestions for the prospective application of the CBP in the agroecology context.

In reflecting upon this transformative journey, it is imperative to highlight two critical considerations. Firstly, there persists a discernible gap in training programmes specifically tailored for the subtleties of the agroecology context, necessitating further research in this domain.

Secondly, the efficacy and success of a training programme hinges on a nuanced understanding of the target group's characteristics, underscoring the importance of a preliminary analysis of specific needs.

While the training initiatives executed during the ALL-Ready project can be deemed successful, it remains paramount to heed the recommendations outlined above for the future application of the CBP in the agroecology context. The journey toward agroecology continues, with an emphasis on refining and adapting capacity building strategies for sustained impact.

8. Annex

8.1 Annex 1: list of capacity building items

- The training course "Understanding Living Lab Concepts and Co-creation" consists of three modules: Module 1, Module 2, Module 3
- Systems thinking module
- The Field Visits
- Learning Roundtables
- Validation of the CBP
- Database of training material (Annex 5)

8.2 Annex 2 post-workshop survey overview

Activity		Post-event survey response rate
Module 1	Exploring Living Lab Concepts and Collaborative Innovation	10 respondents
Module 2	Exploring Living Lab Concepts and Collaborative Innovation	6 respondents
Module 3	Exploring Living Lab Concepts and Collaborative Innovation	10 respondents
Systems Thinking		11 respondents
Final workshop	Capacity building programme validation	12 respondents

Module 1

Number of participants: 18 pilot network members

Trainers: 3

Organisers: 2

Feedback form: 10 responses

Participants evaluated the overall usefulness for each training module presentation, indicating that:

Part 1, Living lab basics was considered moderately useful and extremely useful by 40% of the participants.

Part 2, Living lab governance and business models resulted to be very useful to 50% of the participants and extremely useful by 30% of the participants.

Participants expressed that part 3, living lab business models, was very useful (50%) and extremely useful (20%).

Graph 6 Module 1 useful evaluation rate

The picture below shows an overview how the training module has improved participants knowledge of the content presented. Half of the respondents (50%) indicated "Living Labs" as the concept that was better improved.

Figure 19 Improved knowledge in module 1

Participants were asked to rate how the training module has helped them expand their knowledge in the following areas: what agroecology is about, knowledge on agroecology research, agroecology farming practices, system thinking and interdisciplinarity and understanding co-creation.

As shown below, while the knowledge on "what agroecology is about", "knowledge on agroecology research", improved moderately in module 1 (respectively 20% and 10%), for 10% of the participants the knowledge on "agroecology farming practices" improved significantly. More positive results concern "systems thinking and interdisciplinarity", which improved significantly (20%) and very significantly (20%) and "understanding co-creation" which improved significantly (40%) and very significantly (10%).

Graph 7 Knowledge improved in module 1 for each competence

Finally, the picture below provides an overview of the extent to which participants expect to use the information received through module 1.

While part 1, Living Lab Basics, was expected to be used by 30 % of participants part 2 and 3, Living Lab governance and business models was expected to be used by 40% of the participants.

50% of the participants expects to use part 3“ LL business models”.

Graph 8 Expectation of using the training module 1

Module 2

Number of participants: 14 pilot network members

Trainers: 2

Organisers: 3

Feedback form: 6 responses

The usefulness score for each training module presentation shows positive results; in fact, all the training sections were evaluated as very useful (average of 33,3% of participants) and extremely useful (average of 25% of participants).

Graph 9 Usefulness score for each topic of the training module 2

Through module 2, the knowledge on “Systems Thinking and interdisciplinarity” increased significantly for 33,3 % of the participants. An interesting result concerns the knowledge on “understanding co-creation” which increased very significantly for 50% of the participants. “Knowledge on agroecology research” improved moderately for 16,7 % of the attendees, while the knowledge on “agroecology farming practices” improved a little for 33,3% of the respondents.

What was particularly appreciated by the participants was the practices approach of the training, which provided examples and exercises to facilitate the understanding.

Graph 10 Knowledge improved in module 2 for each competence

Among the concepts discussed during the training, 33,3% of the respondents indicated that they intend to put the knowledge on “Innovation Management”, “Panel Management”, “Pilot Management” and the “Impact assessment” into practice.

Module 3

Number of participants: 26

Feedback form: 10 responses

The feedback forms highlighted the following:

6 LL and 4 RI answered the feedback forms, sharing a general satisfaction in the topics of the training:

- Session 1: Introduction to the Living Lab Model (30% very useful, 30% moderately useful, 40% slightly useful)
- Session 2: Co-creation and Real-Life experimentation (20% very useful, 40% moderately useful, 20% slightly useful, 20% not useful at all)
- Session 3: Facilitation Technique (10% extremely useful, 10 % very useful, 40% moderately useful, 20% slightly useful, 10% not useful at all)

Graph 11 Level of satisfaction of the module 3

The image below illustrates the extent to which the training module has enhanced participants' understanding of the presented content. Notably, 30% of the respondents mentioned that their comprehension of "facilitation techniques" saw the most significant improvement.

Graph 12 Knowledge gained by participants in module 3

For most of the participants, the knowledge on "What agroecology is about", "knowledge on agroecology research" and "agroecology farming practice" improved moderately. Knowledge of systems thinking and interdisciplinarity and 'understanding co-creation' was significantly improved by 10% of participants.

Considering the topics discussed during the training, 10% of participants are expecting to use the concept of the "Living Lab Model" and "Co-creation and Real-Life Experimentation" very significantly. 20% of the respondents are considering using the "Facilitation Techniques" concept.

Graph 13 Expectation of using the knowledge gained from the training module 3

Systems thinking trainings

Number of participants: 26

Feedback received: 11

9. To what extent do you expect to use the information obtained through the training module?

■ Not at all ■ Slightly ■ Moderately ■ Significantly ■ Very Significantly

Graph 14 Expectation of using the knowledge gained from the systems thinking training

Final workshop at OLLD

Number of responses received: 9 + 3 not present

This last workshop received very positive feedback concerning the usefulness of the concepts discussed

■ Not at all useful ■ Slightly useful ■ Moderately useful ■ Very useful ■ Extremely useful

Graph 15 usefulness rate of the final workshop

8.3 Annex 3 Overview of the results of the interactive activity of the co-design of the capacity building (21-23 November 2022)

Practical farming skills

- To add: Farm PEP (performance enhancement platform): a Wikipedia-style website on farming practices, events, researchers, farmers
- To add: toolbox within the IPM works project on IPM materials from 5 different databases
- Calendar for practical events
- Necessary to be expressed in the “target idioms”
- Testimonials are not enough evidence for improvement
- Who is this targeted to? Who would have access to these? Hopefully not just members of the LL/RI network, they often involve forward thinking, AE farmers; needs to be accessible to other farmers, agronomists etc...
- Exchange with AKIS, projects.

Common understanding of agroecology

- LLAEBIO has ppt explaining AE with examples (NL) to add
- Very much related with knowledge on AE research: illustrate AE with scientific proof
- Merge knowledge for researchers, farmers, LLs, and all pilot levels
- Showing quantitative results
- Economic agroecosystems

Knowledge on AE research

- Organic Eprints to add
- EU Farm book to add
- Links with practical AE farming skills
- Filter on practical manuals
- Results are not dividable between practical farming and research results
- What with overlap with other databases, e.g., organic farm knowledge?
- Know the language of the tool
- Find results in an easy way by using key words/filters:

Methodologies

End users of the resource

AE concept, principles

Co-creation

- ALL-Ready has already established an ecosystem of actors of co-creation, use it.
- How to collect data from co-creation settings, e.g., to publish?
- Theoretical background docs to add
- Toolbox made available with practical participation examples.
- Templates to evaluate how the LL went.
- Templates to arrange effective farmer-to-farmer events.

- Media kit for creating farming ambassadors.
- Workshop to address challenges of the network members as they arise.
- Use best tools of LIAISON project: their guide is not so user friendly, so more rearrangement would be useful to signpost people to the tool/exercise that is most useful for them.

Systems thinking:

- Yes, for different levels.
- Yes, we need it now for the food system partnership.
- System boundaries (change the thinking)
- Feedback and loops in the system
- Inclusion/exclusion (selection of relevant elements)
- Agree with a new course/training.
- Beyond the system in an AE context
- Methodologies
- How to frame the problem?

Figure 20 A selection of photos taken during the interactive activity

8.4 Annex 4 Agenda of the Validation workshop

Welcome and introduction of the meeting
Capacity Building Programme – Looking back.... Review of capacity building programme
Capacity Building Programme – Looking back.... Storytelling from Pilot Network Members (PNMs) to hear about experiences applying the knowledge they received in the trainings: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• What concept/tool they applied, who was the targeted audience/group, how they applied it, what worked/what did not
Small group discussions Topic: How to better adapt the capacity building to the agroecology sector/local context Subtopics: <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Generic conversation around how to apply methodologies/concepts to agroecology. For example, governance model, business model, stakeholders' engagement, systems thinking, etc.<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Question 1 - Which methodology or concept presented in the trainings did you find most interesting?• Question 2 – Do you find this methodology or concept easy or difficult to adapt? Do you see relationships between the methodologies/concept and AE principles? Which of the presented methodology or concept is the easiest/most difficult to adapt?• Question 3 – When (at which stage) would you use it as a methodology? Who would be your target group of stakeholders?• Question 4 - What do you recommend for adapting this tool/technique to the context of AE?2. Examine a particular facilitation tool/technique and get recommendations for applicability in local context<ul style="list-style-type: none">• First select a facilitation tool/technique to discuss (e.g., Funeral technique)• Question 1 – Why is this tool easy/difficult to apply in your local context?• Question 2 – When (at which stage) would you use it? With whom?• Question 3 - What do you recommend for adapting this tool/technique to the context of AE
Report back Each facilitator shares what 2 highlights from the discussion
Explanation of the peer-to-peer exchange <ul style="list-style-type: none">• In groups of 4. Each group of PNMs will be picked at random.• PNMs will have 3 rounds of peer-consulting with other PNMs

- The discussion is facilitated through a provided set of questions
- For each group: 1 facilitator to guide the conversation/ask questions, and 1 notetaker to collect main points of discussion

Coffee Break

Peer-to-peer exchange

Round 1: 10:50 - 11:20 – Questions 1

Round 2: 11:20 - 11:50 – Questions 2

Round 3: 11:50 - 12:15 – Questions 3

Each round focused on a particular set of questions. PNMs can bring specific examples from their experience to exchange and learn from one another.

1. How do you make sure that stakeholders are engaged in your LL/RI? How do you retain them (what are the incentives you use)?
2. How do you organise field visits? How do you engage stakeholders during field visits (what do you do)? What constitutes a good/successful field visit and why? How would you integrate the concepts/methodologies or tools/techniques in the field visit?
3. How do you measure and evaluate the impact of your LL/RI? What are the KPIs, how do you track success, etc What are some best practices or lessons learned for long-term sustainability (operational, financial, etc) of your LL/RI?

Report back

Each facilitator or a PNM share what 1-2 highlights from each round of discussion

Next steps

8.5 Annex 5 Database of training material

See below

Main topic : Knowledge on AE Research

Sub topic (select which sub topic the material falls best under: Knowledge on socio-economic assessments in agroecology related research OR Knowledge on monitoring/measurements of carbon sequestration, (soil) biodiversity, GHG emissions, etc: indicators and results	Format (video, e-course, database, etc)	Material description	Target audience	Language availability	Duration to view / review material (mins)	Material Owner (your organisation or another)	Link to ressource
EXAMPLE Knowledge on socio-economic assessments in agroecology related research	Video Recording	Video course of	Policy-Makers, LL coordinators	EN, FR	60	ENoLL	www.enoll.org
Knowledge on monitoring/measurements	ppt	Not really monitoring/measurements, but we have knowledge on on-farm research methodology in form of a ppt which might be turned into a written material	Researcher, farmers	HU, EN	5 min	ÖMKi	https://www.biokutatas.hu/en/page/show/onfarm
Knowledge on socio-economic assessments in agroecology related research	PhD, written material	by Flemish beef farmers. Research aimed at investigating the relevance of agroecology to Flemish beef farming. More specific research questions were: what actions can and do these beef farmers take to put agroecology into practice; what is the role of these	Researchers	EN		EV ILVO	agroeological principles by Flemish beef farmers : advancing towards a body of thought for sustainable
Knowledge on monitoring/measurements	survey/D1.1	WP1 material ALL-Ready: evaluation of LL/RI	Researchers	EN		INRAE	
Knowledge on monitoring/measurements		Tool for Agroecology Performance Evaluation (TAPE)	Researchers	EN		FAO	How it works Agroecology Knowledge Hub Food and
Knowledge on monitoring/measurements	video	Le diagnostic agriculture paysanne	Farm advisors	FR	5 min	FADEAR Réseau de l'agriculture paysanne	Le Diagnostic Agriculture paysanne
(provided by Torsten - didn't specify a subtheme)	Report	Green biorefining of grassland biomass	Policy extension etc	EN		DCA	UNISECO project? https://ocp.potsdam.edu/dk/djfpublikation/index.asp?action=show&id=1480
(provided by Torsten - didn't specify a subtheme)		DCA rapport, nr. 193, 2021					
(provided by Torsten - didn't specify a subtheme)	Report	Soil Compaction	Policy, extension	EN		DCA	https://ocp.potsdam.edu/dk/djfpublikation/index.asp?action=show&id=1306
(provided by Torsten - didn't specify a subtheme)		DCA rapport, nr. 155, 2019					

(provided by Torsten - didn't specify a subtheme)	Report	Mapping sustainability criteria for the bioeconomy	Policy, extension	EN		DCA	https://ocp.psu.dk/djfpublikation/index.asp?action=show&id=1213
(provided by Torsten - didn't specify a subtheme)		DCA rapport, nr. 76, 2016					
(provided by Stephane - didn't specify a subtheme)	E book		researchers, policy makers	EN, FR		Inrae/ Quae	https://www.quae-open.com/produit/158/9782759232949/agroecology-

Main topic : Agroecology practical farming skills and knowledge

No subtopic for this one	Format (video, e-course, database, etc)	Material description	Target audience	Language availability	Duration to view / review material (mins)	Material Owner (your organisation or another)	Link to ressource
EXAMPLE Agroecology practical farming skills and knowledge	Video Recording	Video course of	Policy-Makers, LL coordinators	EN, FR	60	ENoLL	www.enoll.org
Agroecology practical farming skills and knowledge	Video recording	Playlist on soil health practices in organic and agroecological farming (half in HU with subtitles, the other half in EN)	Farmers	HU, EN	av. 30 min/video	ÖMKi	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9SM81QCrajM&list=PLAKR11cz4fOJjHAAOn9RthurPXIXQMa
Agroecology practical farming skills and knowledge	Video Recording	Playlist on proper seed treatment, storage and seed saving (half in HU with subtitles, the other half in EN)	Farmers, seed companies	HU, EN	av. 15 min/video	ÖMKi	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=8SbfIQvwQ5A&list=PLAKR11cz4fOKg_j
Agroecology practical farming skills and knowledge	Video Recording	Videos consisting a wide range of organic and agroecological practices from crop production, animal husbandry, farm/food chain management etc.	Farmers, food chain companies	EN, FR, HU, IT, DE, ES, BG, FN, CZ, ET, LT	av. 15 min/video	Organic Farm Knowledge Platform	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCCKA7IMg-4SxmWbxYQzjfjEw
Agroecology practical farming skills and knowledge	Publications	Downloadable publications on various organic farming practices and techniques from crop production, cover cropping, apiculture, viticulture to horticulture	Farmers	HU	90 min	ÖMKi	https://www.biokutatas.hu/hu/webshop/index/kiadvany/
Agroecology practical farming skills and knowledge	Learning platform	Platform Organic Farm Knowledge: a platform providing access to a wide range of tools and resources about organic farming that can help improve production. It also aims to serve as a virtual meeting place for cross-border learning.					https://organic-farmknowledge.org/
(provided by Torsten - didn't specify a subtheme)		DCA rapport, nr. 121, 2018	Extension, farmers	EN		DCA	https://dcapubs.au.dk/djfpublikation/index.asp?action=show&id=1262
Agroecology practical farming skills and knowledge	video recording	videos	farmers, extensionnists	FR	as a whole hours and days!	Ver de Terre Production	https://www.verdetereprod.fr/videos/

Main topic : What agroecology is about								
Sub topic : Common understanding about agroecology and agroecology transition (agroecology as an evolving concept, different perceptions on agroecology, towards a shared understanding of agroecology)	Format (video, e-course, database, etc)	Material description	Target audience	Language availability	Duration to view / review material (mins)	Material Owner (your organisation or another)	Link to ressource	
EXAMPLE Common understanding about agroecology and agroecology transition (agroecology as an evolving concept, different perceptions on agroecology, towards a shared understanding of agroecology)	Video Recording	Video course of	Policy-Makers, LL coordinators	EN, FR	60	ENoLL	www.enoll.org	
Common understanding about agroecology and agroecology transition (agroecology as an evolving concept, different perceptions on agroecology, towards a shared understanding of agroecology)	MOOC (Montpellier SupAgro)	Agroecology, an introduction			6 weeks course	Montpellier SupAgro	Agroecology, an introduction (fun-mooc.fr)	
Common understanding about agroecology and agroecology transition (agroecology as an evolving concept, different perceptions on agroecology, towards a shared understanding of agroecology)		Agroecology and the reconstruction of post COVID 19 agriculture and food system - "talking about the agroecology contributions, agricultural practices, animals, consumers,... mainly the section about amplification of agroecology"		English		University of California and CELIA	Miguel Altieri: Agroecology and the reconstruction of a post Covid-19 agriculture - YouTube	
Common understanding about agroecology and agroecology transition (agroecology as an evolving concept, different perceptions on agroecology, towards a shared understanding of agroecology)		Agroecology and the reconstruction of post COVID 19 agriculture and food system - Miguel Altieri. AGROECOLOGÍA ¿Para qué?, ¿Para quienes?, ¿Para cuántos? - YouTube - (Spanish speaker) this video talks about the difficulties in agroecology and agroecology in practice		Spanish		University of California and CELIA	Miguel Altieri. AGROECOLOGÍA ¿Para qué?, ¿Para quienes?, ¿Para cuántos? - YouTube	
Common understanding about agroecology and agroecology transition (agroecology as an evolving concept, different perceptions on agroecology, towards a shared understanding of agroecology)		Agroecology: Farmers' pathways to liberation from pesticides - Speakers talking about the transition between industrial agriculture and agroecology and outcomes obtain. (in 3 languages)		Spanish		PAN (Pesticide Action Network)	Agroecology Webinars & Videos - YouTube	
Common understanding about agroecology and agroecology transition (agroecology as an evolving concept, different perceptions on agroecology, towards a shared understanding of agroecology)		La casa encendida - Agroecology and practical examples in Latin American agriculture with respective evidence and results against climate change				Casa encendida	Agroecología y cambio climático, Masterclass con Clara Nicholls - YouTube	
Common understanding about agroecology and agroecology transition (agroecology as an evolving concept, different perceptions on agroecology, towards a shared understanding of agroecology)	E-course	FAO - 40 h course, online			40h course	FAO	action/capacitacion-politicas-publicas/cursos/ver/es/c/1412359/	
Common understanding about agroecology and agroecology transition (agroecology as an evolving concept, different perceptions on agroecology, towards a shared understanding of agroecology)		It talks about the agroecology principles and applications		Spanish		BID (Banco interamericano de desarrollo)	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ip0Y5G_Ri6A	
Common understanding about agroecology and agroecology transition (agroecology as an evolving concept, different perceptions on agroecology, towards a shared understanding of agroecology)		General vision about the agroecology				University (Centre for Agroecology, Water and	/watch?v=pWrsqgzZwYA&list=PLvjHiv2S9PdXHkrZK82Y9dyUOX_n70YJm&index=6	
Common understanding about agroecology and agroecology transition (agroecology as an evolving concept, different perceptions on agroecology, towards a shared understanding of agroecology)	E-course				6 week course on soil and climate	FAO	https://www.agropolis.org/training/mooc.php	

Common understanding about agroecology and agroecology transition (agroecology as an evolving concept, different perceptions on agroecology, towards a shared understanding of agroecology)	E-course	LIFT H2020				hour about Sustainable Food Value Chains for	FAO	https://elearning.fao.org/course/view.php?id=566
Common understanding about agroecology and agroecology transition (agroecology as an evolving concept, different perceptions on agroecology, towards a shared understanding of agroecology)	E-learning catalogue	FAO e-learning catalogue with dozens of educational material on food and nutrition				catalogue with dozens of educational material on	FAO	ocal/search/?src=evJ0ZXN0byl6liIsInNlcmllcyl6liIsInJlbGVhc2VkyXRlIjoiiwibGluZ3VhlioiZW4iLCJpc25ldyI6lii
Common understanding about agroecology and agroecology transition (agroecology as an evolving concept, different perceptions on agroecology, towards a shared understanding of agroecology)	MOOC	not directly accessible, needs registration					LIFT H2020	https://www.lift-h2020.eu/mooc-2-2/
Common understanding about agroecology and agroecology transition (agroecology as an evolving concept, different perceptions on agroecology, towards a shared understanding of agroecology)								
(provided by Torsten - didn't specify a subtheme)	Videos	'Understanding Agroecology' videos which, produced by keen PhD students, are both didactic and characterized by some degree of levity.						https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCR2O0VSu0rgi2VIC09A5Trw/playlists?view=50&sort=dd&shelf_id=3
	Videos	USDA's Climate, Agriculture, and Forest Science Webinar Series					USDA	usda.gov/hubs/topic/usdas-climate-agriculture-and-forest-science-webinar-series
Common understanding about agroecology and agroecology transition (agroecology as an evolving concept, different perceptions on agroecology, towards a shared understanding of agroecology)	mooc on agroecology	on line course	all publics	FR, EN, Spanish (latin america)	24 hours in 6 weeks	Institut Agro Montpellier France		https://www.fun-mooc.fr/fr/cours/agroecologie/
Common understanding about agroecology and agroecology transition (agroecology as an evolving concept, different perceptions on agroecology, towards a shared understanding of agroecology)	learning in agroecology	Video course of	all publics	FR	6 minutes	Terre et Humanisme		https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=dGU7VGxtcSo

Main topic : Systems thinking and interdisciplinarity								
No subtopic for this one	Format (video, e-course, database, etc)	Material description	Target audience	Language availability	Duration to view / review material (mins)	Material Owner (your organisation or another)	Link to ressource	
EXAMPLE Systems thinking and interdisciplinarity	Video Recording	Video course of	Policy-Makers, LL coordinators	EN, FR	60	ENoLL	www.enoll.org	
Systems thinking and interdisciplinarity	E-course/PPT	Introduction to systems thinking (what, why, how)	all	NL		EV ILVO		
Systems thinking and interdisciplinarity	No formal video recording		PhD students	EN, FR		IFSA European Group	http://ifsa.boku.ac.at/cms/index.php?id=138	

Main topic : Understanding co-creation

Sub topic (select which sub topic the material falls best under: Setting up living labs: governance models, evaluation of performance of LL OR Facilitation skills in co-creation settings)	Format (video, e-course, database, etc)	Material description	Target audience	Language availability	Duration to view / review material (mins)	Material Owner (your organisation or another)	Link to resource
EXAMPLE Facilitation skills in co-creation settings	Video Recording	Video course of	Policy-Makers, LL coordinators	EN, FR	60	ENoLL	www.enoll.org
	Guides/Handbooks	LIAISON's guides on how to do co-creation from building enabling environment for participants to evaluation	LL/RI coordinators, researchers	EN	90 min	LIAISON project (Soil Association)	https://liaison2020.eu/your-material/?language=english
	Handbook	Good practices and methods for co-creation	LL/RI coordinators, researchers	EN	90 min	RICHEs project	riches-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2015/12/RICHES-D4-
	Pdf material	Methods and tips for online engagement and facilitation	LL/RI coordinators, researchers, policy makers,	EN	40 min	ÖMKi	enclosed
Facilitation Skills in co-creation settings	Training I2connect	training to fuel competencies of advisors and their organisations to engage and support farmers in interactive innovation processes	farm advisors; LL/RI coordinators	EN		I2connect	i2connect - Home - i2connect (i2connect-h2020.eu)
Setting up LLs	Project publication (can be translated into peer to peer exchange on 'how to support on-farm experiments')	Good practices and methods for supporting farmers in their transition to agroecology (more specifically: how to set up on-farm experiments)	farm advisors; LL/RI coordinators; researchers	NL/FR		TRANSÆ	Contact Transæ Transition vers l'agro-écologie